

Entropy, Time Reversal Balanced Reactions and Information

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Statistical mechanics often focuses on entropy which is related to maximizing the number of possible states subject to constraints. Alternatively, Shannon's entropy $S = -k \sum P_i \ln(P_i)$ where P_i are probabilities is used. This maximization leads to Maxwell-Boltzmann's (MB) distribution (and also the Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) distributions). Even though maximization of entropy does not deal with the idea of reactions occurring, it seems natural that particles move from some states to others. Thus, there should be a dynamical picture related to reactions which may also lead to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (and also the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions). Time reversal balance of say elastic two body collisions is such a dynamical picture, but it seems different from the idea of maximum entropy, at least on the surface. With the entropy approach, average energy is a constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$, but in the reaction approach one insists on elastic collisions.

In this note, we focus on the idea of information (which exists in the literature). In particular, we consider information in gases to be energy. Thus, conservation of energy in an elastic collision may alternatively be looked upon as conservation of information. For the entropy approach, the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ brings in the information.

We argue in this note that information is an independent way of considering equilibrium. Furthermore, we argue that in equilibrium there is a function $g(f(e_i))$ related to an "adjusted" reaction probability which is equivalent to information. For an MB gas $g(f(e_i))$ is $\ln(f(e_i))$, for a Fermi-Dirac gas it is $\ln[f(e_i)/(1-f(e_i))]$ and for a Bose-Einstein gas $\ln[f(e_i) / (1+f(e_i))]$. The idea seems to be that for two particle collisions (as an example), if one has information (energy) before the reaction of E (one may have any product combinations of $g(f(e_i))g(f(e_j))$ such that $e_i+e_j=E$ and these have the same probability. The same result holds for the reactants. Thus, energy e being the "information" in a problem really means that one does not distinguish between $g(e_i)g(e_j)$ if $e_i+e_j=E$. This we argue is a different way of characterizing equilibrium situations from the traditional entropy maximization approach and time reversal balance reactions. This does not mean that one does not need information about the rules which apply to reactions (i.e. the Pauli exclusion rule or the boson enhancement rule). These may be formulated in a way that they may be applied to the counting states in the entropy approach. For example, for a Fermi-Dirac (FD) the occupation of states is 0 or 1. These rules must be known, but it seems that equilibrium forms through the identification of a quantity called information which is conserved in reactions and does not allow one to distinguish between certain probabilities which are all linked to the same E .

Maximum Entropy and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

Writing factorial expressions for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas (or a Fermi-Dirac or a Bose-Einstein gas) and maximizing with respect to a constraint (usually $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$) to find $f(e_i)$ seems to be a standard approach in statistical mechanics (1). It seems as if maximizing entropy i.e. maximizing the probability of a distribution of energy $f(e_i)$ represents the underlying

physics. For example, if there are N particles and the probability to have a particle with energy e_i is $f(e_i)$ then:

$$\text{Probability} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } f(e_i)^{Nf(e_i)} \quad ((1))$$

$Nf(e_i)$ is the number of particles having energy e_i if N is the total number of particles and N is very large. ((1)) may be written as $\exp(\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i)))$ leading to:

$$\text{Shannon's entropy} = -k\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i)) \quad ((2))$$

For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas one adds the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i f(e_i)$ almost trivially and upon maximization finds:

$$\ln(f(e_i)) = -b e_i \text{ or } f(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((3))$$

We argue that e_i is actually important as it is the "information" in the system. By examining ((3)) one may see that if two or more particles were to collide and one is told that the initial state had a total energy (or information of E), any $e_i+e_j=E$ would have the same probability, with the same condition holding for the reactants. This statement seems to be completely different from the idea of maximizing the probability (or number of states) subject to a constraint. The idea of entropy does not explicitly include any notion of collisions or information. As noted, the energy constraint is almost trivial, yet it seems that information (energy) is the central idea of the equilibrium problem and enters through this constraint.

If one considers a FD or BE gas, then $f(e_i)$ is not $\exp(-e_i/T)$, but there is another function (related to probabilities) which is i.e. $f(e_i)/[1-f(e_i)]$ for the FD case and $f(e_i)/[1+f(e_i)]$ for the BE case. Again, energy is information and dictates the basic form of the equilibrium namely that if $e_i + e_j = E$, all $g(f(e_i))g(f(e_j))$ such that $e_i+e_j=E$ have equal probability with an equivalent condition holding for the reactants. It seems that this is an alternative approach to defining equilibrium which is unusual because $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$ i.e. conservation of energy is used in deterministic classical mechanics. Nevertheless, one must know about all of the probabilities related to a reaction occurring i.e. a particle leaving an e_i state and going to another. For a Fermi-Dirac gas, $f(e_i)$ is the probability that a particle will leave e_i , but $(1-f(e_i))$ is a suppression factor (unnormalized probability) which prevents the particle from leaving (i.e. another from entering state e_i). Thus, it seems that one may actually look at one particle and find probabilities which depend on e_i (through $f(e_i)$) in order to find $g(f(e_i))$.

Time Reversal Reaction Balance

Although the entropy maximization approach uses factorials to count the number of possible states (1), we argued in (2) that one may use time reversal reaction balance and bypass this completely. The idea is that for two body collisions (for example), the probability for a given e_i and e_j to form an e_k and e_l where $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$ must be balanced by the probability of the time reversed reaction. In such a case, every e_i,e_j pair which converts to e_k,e_l is matched by an e_k,e_l pair combining into e_i,e_j ensuring all $f(e_i)$'s remain constant. The time reversal reactions are:

MB $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$ FD $f(e_i)[1-f(e_k)] f(e_j)[1-f(e_l)] = f(e_k)[1-f(e_i)] f(e_l)[1-f(e_j)]$ and

BE $f(e_i)[1+f(e_k)] f(e_j)[1+f(e_l)] = f(e_k)[1+f(e_i)] f(e_l)[1+f(e_j)]$ ((4))

In such a manner, one may find the MB, FD and BE distributions. We argue, however, that the key idea is still energy as information. There is a function $g(f(e_i))$, a generalized reaction probability such that $\ln(g(f(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ where T is temperature. In order to find $g(f(e_i))$ one must be aware of the physical constraints in the system. For example, for an FD gas one may not scatter into a state which is occupied. This is approximated by $f(e_i)[1-f(e_k)]$ for e_i scattering into e_k . For the BE case there is an enhancement $f(e_i)[1+f(e_k)]$. Nevertheless, the various product type reaction probabilities lead to a general form:

$g(f(e_i)) g(f(e_j)) = g(f(e_k)) g(f(e_l))$ where $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$ ((5))

In such a case, any $e_i+e_j=E$ has the same probability before the collision and any $e_k+e_l=E$ after. Thus, energy as information being conserved in equilibrium is again the key idea. It seems that because $e_i+e_j = e_k + e_l$ is already known as a physical law i.e. conservation of energy in classical mechanics, that one may not think of it as conservation of information in a statistical problem.

As a result, both the entropy maximization approach and reaction balance approach seem to be linked to a conservation of information (energy).

It is interesting to consider entropy in the FD case as an example. One may calculate the number of states as done in (1) and obtain $f(e_i)$, but given that $g(f(e_i)) = f(e_i) / [1-f(e_i)]$ one may note that there are two probabilities in the problem $f(e_i)$ and $[1-f(e_i)]$ (unnormalized probability which prevents decay from the state e_i while $f(e_i)$ is proportional to the probability for decay). Thus, one may have two Shannon's entropy terms:

S density = $f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i)) + (1-f(e_i)) \ln[1-f(e_i)]$ ((6))

It should also be noted that the entropy approach is not completely separate from time reversal balance. In the former, one considers states so there should be a mechanism (e.g. scattering) for particles to move from one to another. In equilibrium, the average number of particles leaving a state e_i , $f(e_i)$ in the MB case, should be balanced by the number of particles entering this state. For a more complicated reaction probability which is the function of various functions of $f(e_i)$ (but all in product form in the reaction equation), taking \ln of the reaction equation leads to a sum of $\ln(g(f(e_i)))$ terms. These are equated to energies e_i because of conservation of energy, but also because energy represents the information associated with state e_i . $f(e_i)$ is the probability for a particle to be a state e_i , but this state is characterized by e_i . The overall rate of leaving state e_i (which may be complicated e.g. $f(e_i)/[1-f(e_i)]$ for the FD case) corresponds to a loss of energy e_i . The two are directly linked.

Idea of Information

If energy is information, then for two particles with e_i and e_j colliding, the total information is $e_i + e_j$ (if information adds as a scalar). This forces all e_i, e_j combinations to have the same probability, otherwise energy $E = e_i + e_j$ would not be the information of the problem, there would be some extra information which would distinguish a particular e_1, e_2 pair ($e_1 + e_2 = E$) or a set of pairs from others. Having $e_i + e_j$ conserved follows from conservation of energy in deterministic classical mechanics, but makes energy a candidate for information in a statistical problem.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that two conceptual ways of considering the origins of $f(e_i)$, the distribution of particles in a state of energy e_i , are the maximization of entropy and time reversal reaction balance. These two appear to be very different conceptually, although there is a connection. We argue in this note that there seems to be an idea underlying both of these namely that of energy as information. The statistical nature of equilibrium seems to be based on energy as the main form of information so that for $e_i + e_j = E$ in the MB case, all e_i and e_j which add to E have equal probability. There is no other information than energy and this does not allow one to distinguish (in terms of probability) between any e_i, e_j pairs. The same idea holds for reactants. In the case of an FD or BE gas, there is again a function $g(f(e_i))$ which has this property.

Thus, the main approach behind equilibrium may not be either maximizing the number of states occupied (entropy) or balancing reactions, but rather thinking in terms of the information in the problem. In the entropy maximization case, information enters through the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ while in the time reversal reaction balance it enters through elastic collisions $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. Both of these seem like straightforward extra conditions, but we argue that they really carry the main idea of equilibrium, namely that energy is information and governs what probabilities may be distinguished. For example, one may distinguish the probability of $e_1 + e_2 = E_1$ from $e_3 + e_4 = E_2$, but one may not distinguish probabilities within either E_1 or E_2 . Nevertheless, one must know details of a reaction. For example, for an MB gas one must know that $f(e_i)$ is the probability to leave state e_i , while for an FD gas $f(e_i)$ is the probability to leave state e_i , while $[1 - f(e_i)]$ is an unnormalized probability blocking the departure. These two must be combined as $f(e_i)/[1 - f(e_i)]$ before one can make the link to information i.e. $\ln [g(f(e_i))] = -e_i/T$.

References

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